

REPRESENTATION OF THE CONCEPT "MUSLIM WORLD" IN A MODERN ENGLISH MEDIADISOURSE

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ANNOTATSIYA

Current article deals with an integrated approach to the study of the concept of "Muslim world", verbalized by means of the English language, using a lingua-confessional approach that allows taking into account the religious side of the issue, as well as political and historical data. Being new in the research it's systematization lexical units that did not previously appear as a separate independent group, united by a common conceptual basis. In addition, the lexicon objectifying the phenomenon the Muslim world, in terms of the potential for manipulative influence

Lingua-confessionalism is one of the lingua-culturological directions, involving the study features of the linguistic representation of the phenomena "language" and "religion", which allows you to be aware, feel and understand the religious and cultural exclusivity and universality (for example, "Christianity - Islam"; "Islam - Judaism", etc.), embodied in a tandem of linguistics and extralinguistics. The subject of lingua-confessiology is the verbal embodiment of lingua-culture, explication of the correlation of religion and all strata national language, and the goal and objectives of this scientific discipline is description of the means, methods and grounds for the formation and updating confessional culture in

language as mechanisms of representation national culture, religious identity, as well as systematization confessionally marked means of all levels of language structure in the universe of the sacred text.

Given the fact that language verbalizes the surrounding reality, it can be noted that the national language abounds means updating basic linguistic concepts, and confessional concepts including. This indicates that all existing in extralinguistic reality images, symbols, associations, concepts, the commandments of any denomination are kept in the people's memory and are transmitted from generation to generation in a coded form of a semiotic system.

The religion of Islam in the West is not a new phenomenon; it was founded with the

very first contacts of European peoples with Arabs. Muslims represent the fastest growing and youngest part population of Great Britain. This is confirmed by the passing time in decade of the census. In modern media discourse, along with the term "Muslim" is often used as "Islamist". Islamists are supporters of Islamization, and Muslims are those who look at the world through the prism of the Qur'an, while counting their relationship with Allah is purely personal. Islamists seek to remake life according to the laws of the Qur'an, interpreting them often quite freely, those who consider these laws are absolute and leaves no room in life for irreligiousness, for the opportunity to coexist with other concepts and views. Thus, Muslims are followers of Islam, believers in one God (Allah) and the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh); Islamists are people with a certain religious and political ideology who believe that any disagreements within society and the state where there is a Muslim population must be decided on the basis of Sharia law that jihad is mandatory against all infidels, in connection with which they, "using specifically interpreted provisions of Sharia, allow the commission of terrorist acts".

Among the features that, in a holistic unity, embody the uniqueness of Islam in the field of the religious experience of mankind and are a presenter of a religious maximalist paradigm capable of ideologically determine the radicalization of consciousness and activity, it should be said that Muslim countries are still guided by religious postulates, on the basis of which secular laws. The sincere confession of religious dogmas is still a distinctive feature of the Muslim environment. It is in

this context that we the concept of "Muslim world" is considered, which is presented in English-language media in a mostly negative light.

From a cultural point of view, Islam represents a huge interest for many scientists. Analysis of the life of the countries of the East was reflected in the works foreign researchers such as Rodinson, Dossa, Karim. Sociologists analyze the attitude in Islam towards women, the way of life within society political scientist - relations between Muslim countries and Western countries, causes of terrorism among Islamists. E.A. Navickaite examines factual material from the point of view expressiveness and evaluativeness and notes that on the expressiveness of the media text is influenced by the intentions of the addressee of the speech act, the initial knowledge and perceptions of the addressee, as well as the linguistic and extralinguistic (social) context of the communicative act. E.A. Navitskaite emphasizes that journalistic articles, as a rule, are distinguished by "special appraisal and expressiveness". The bias problem mass consciousness is also reflected in his works where the question is raised about the choice of lexical means, such as a metaphor, epithet, comparison and syntactic constructions, the use of which associated with "manipulation of public opinion". In addition to lexical and syntactic means of expressing expressiveness in the media, specific techniques are also often used that do not have counterparts in oral speech, for example, the use of quotation marks when it comes to Islamic science, which the scientist does not consider as such. According to some researchers'

consideration, the crisis periods and problems of the development of spirituality in Islam. However, the authors state that at the present time Islam stands on flowering paths. Experts characterize the modern round in history Islam as "revival", "renaissance". Media discourse, like a single text, always assumes that information is transmitted by a narrow group of people, while it is perceived she's a lot of people. At the moment there are several approaches to the interpretation of this concept. According to one of them, media discourse is a special type of speech-thinking activity, which characteristic of the information field of mass media. With this interpretation distinguish between media discourse and other types of discourse (political, religious, scientific, etc.). Utterances from different discourses can belong to a common thematic layer, while differences between them are based on the modification of some parameters of the discourse: different language practices, different communication situations its implementation. The second approach is that media discourse considered as any kind of discourse, while it exists in the mass communication that is broadcast through the media, that is, it represents a speech-thinking activity in the media space, to which includes the Internet. The Internet is a tool communication (electronic channel) for data transmission, respectively Internet discourse is a kind of media discourse.

We adhered to the second point view, bearing in mind that media discourse is "thematically focused, sociocultural conditioned speech-thinking activity in mass media space. The main difference between this species discourse is the creation of ideas about the ways of

transferring knowledge, in addition to their production. The concept indicated by the term "concept" is multifaceted, and there are different interpretations of this term. So, we will adhere to the following definition: concept is a constituent unit of the concept system (the semantic model of the main worldview concepts), which is objectified in the word, language in the form sensory and mental signs of a phenomenon reality and represents these signs through the text as mental, historical and ethnic signs in the minds of the people, where "the core is gradually enveloped, enveloped in layers of conceptual signs that increases the volume of the concept and saturates its content.

Conducted conceptual analysis, including etymological and component analysis (based on dictionary definitions), makes it possible to designate the core of the concept "Muslim" as "someone whose religion is Islam"; analysis of the lexeme "World" shows that the core is "The planet that we live on". Accordingly, the core of the "Muslim world" concept is the concept of the totality of all those people on the planet who profess Islam, as well as their followers. If we combine the meanings of the words "Muslim" and "World", then the concept of "Muslim world" is presented as everything that in one way or another describes the very phenomenon of the Muslim world: these are lexemes for denoting everyday life, psychology, ethnography, objects of the material and categories of the spiritual world.

Based on the conducted definitional analysis of the above lexemes, it can be argued that the core of the concept is formed by the idea of a group of people / community / generation that are connected by ideas (the people or things belonging to

a particular group or connected with a particular interest or job in Oxford Advanced language Dictionary, a particular area of activity or work and the people who are involved in it Longman Academic Advanced Dictionary; a distinctive class of persons or their sphere of interest in Merriam Webster Dictionary . The dictionary interpretation of the lexemes "Muslim" and "World" indicates that the concept of "Muslim world" appears in a certain historical period (and a particular period in history and the society and people of that time (LAAD); a particular period of history and the people of that period (OALD); generation of the inhabitants of the earth distinguished by living together at the same place or at the same time (MWD)), that every Muslim must follow - this is the Muslim way of life. Thus, the conceptual attribute "LIFESTYLE / MUSLIMS CULTURE" and Sharia are correlated with each other. Sharia is the religious and ethical basis of Islam, which also includes work, everyday life, and the rules of human behavior. The Muslim way of life is impossible without the characteristics of the way of life of the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh). The image of the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh), his activities are ideal for all believers.

The lifestyle of Muslims, in turn, makes it possible to judge the presence of such a conceptual area as certain conditions of realization for a particular way of life (and a particular type of place or situation; the kind of life we have (LAAD)). The conceptual feature "CONDITIONS OF IMPLEMENTATION" is correlate of all kinds of situations necessary for the implementation of any action. To create such conditions, it is necessary to have knowledge and skills, and knowledge in

Islam is considered as an obligation and dignity. Throughout his life, a Muslim person must learn new things and strive for science, which will become a certain condition for the realization of his goals. Education in Islam is seen as the knowledge of the values of Islam and as improvement of a person in terms of his morality. Not all knowledge is recognized as beneficial in Islam. In the Sunnah there are the words of the Prophet regarding knowledge: "There are four vices of knowledge: this is boasting of one's knowledge and a feeling of superiority in front of recognized scholars; using knowledge in competition with fools; attempts to achieve through knowledge the benevolence of the leaders - people occupying an influential position". Thus, the unity of mind (knowledge), soul and body (skills and abilities) in Islam has the abbreviation ADAB - adab. Adab is not only the result of education, but also a method of cognition, with the help of which students actualize knowledge, attitudes and activities. The mandatory sign "CONDITIONS OF REALIZATION" is correlated through Adab.

The environment of an individual, that is, his family, friends is characterized through the concept of the "Muslim world" (and a person's environment, experiences, friends and family (OALD), the society that we live in (LAAD)). This makes it possible to identify such a conceptual area as society.

The main values for Muslims are the family and the hierarchy of relationships within the family. The foundations of justice and social status are initially laid in the family, and then transferred to society and implemented there. Hence follows the obligatory sign "SOCIETY" - it is a

conceptual correlate of the society that surrounds the Muslim.

The concept of "Muslim World" is structurally hierarchical organization of mandatory and optional features. Mandatory features of the concept "Muslim World", forming a cognitive propositional frame, serve as a means of actualizing any situation for this concept. Optional signs, in contrast to the mandatory ones, clarify the structure of the concept, complement it and appear depending on a particular situation.

Thus, the analysis of information contained in the explanatory English-English dictionaries, dictionaries of compatibility, and factual material makes it possible to highlight the mandatory features of the concept "Muslim peace". Such signs of the concept are "LIFESTYLE / MUSLIMS CULTURE", "REALIZATION CONDITIONS", "SOCIETY". Among the optional features, one can single out the "SPIRITUAL OR MATERIAL WORLD OF ISLAM", the correlates of which are spiritual values (Allah, prophets, jihad, hajj, namaz, Sharia, etc.) or material values of Islam (household items, monuments architecture, etc.). "ATTITUDE" and "EVALUATION", which in turn are subdivided into "POSITIVE", "NEGATIVE", were also classified as optional features. The perception of the world, being a conceptual correlate of the attribute "ATTITUDE", manifests itself not only with the religious point of view, but also at the ethnic level. Judgment is a conceptual correlate of the optional attribute "EVALUATION", which can be expressed as a defense of Islam or as terrorism and Islamophobia.

The prototypical unit of the concept "Muslim world" is the noun Islam, since it in its most general form reveals the

phenomenon itself and encompasses the meanings of all lexical units representing the concept. The lexeme Islam has several meanings. The most widespread in Western discourse and, perhaps, the most inaccurate translation from Arabic is "obedience", another option is "surrender (entrustment, submission of oneself) to God." Another meaning is "peace", "peaceful", since the words "Islam" and "salam" (which means "peace" in translation) have a common root and are close in their philosophical content.

Thus, the concept of "Islam" already has several meanings in itself. Islam can be perceived in a negative sense - as a threat and danger, that is, the attitude towards the countries of the Muslim world is represented in the texts of the Internet discourse using significant parts of speech with negative connotations:

(1) ... the nation's enemies are a small group of terrorists who have distorted Islam ... [The United States and the Muslim World].

In this example, the nouns "enemies", "terrorist" play the role of negative markers, which also emphasizes the presence of the verb "distorted", which shows how much harm was done to the religion.

(2) Does not say that millions of Muslims who have settled in Europe ought to be deported, taking their "retarded" culture with them.

Negative extinguishment towards Muslims is expressed by modal the construction "ought to be deported" and is complemented by the adjective "retarded", which characterizes the entire Islamic culture.

A group of words capable of verbalizing the concept of the Muslim world" includes such

linguistic units as: Allah, ayatollah, dervish, fatva, hadith, hajj, hajji, hijab, imam. Jihad, Koran (Quran), the Mohammed (pbuh), mosque, mufti, mujaheddin, mullah(prayer), purdah, the Ramadan, sharia, sheikh, Shia, Sunni, veil, yashmak, etc. The most common concept in English-language Internet media is the word "jihad". The "Muslim world" is actualized through the nuclear lexeme "jihad". Let's turn to its dictionary interpretation. The Oxford Advance Learner's Dictionary offers two definitions: Jihad n 1) (in Islam) a spiritual struggle within yourself to stop yourself breaking religious or moral laws', 2) a holy war fought by Muslims to defend Islam.

English-language Internet media, covering the topic of relations with the countries of the Muslim world, present jihad in an unfavourable light, that is, it is verbalized through lexical units with negative connotations. In turn, the lexeme "jihad" actualizes the optional attribute "ASSESSMENT- NEGATIVE" through the meaning "terrorism":

Above given examples, the technique of "transfer" is also observed, when the concept of patriot in combination with the ethno-nomination Muslim is desacralized and evokes negative associations associated with terrorism and jihad. In this way, the media space constantly supports the English-speaking population, aggression and hostility towards Muslims is not allowing them to see the positive side

of the overwhelming the majority of Muslims.

In conclusion, the study of the verbalization of the concept of "Muslim world" in a virtual communicative space allows us to better understand the modern English-speaking picture of the world and present political and ethnic metamorphoses in the language and culture of Britain. Analysis of the complex structural organization of the concept "Muslim World" according to the prototypical principle makes it possible to consider the main layer of vocabulary, representing it with its systemic and functional meaning, and to classify the representatives according to the principle of "prototype - core - periphery ", to present the semantic differentiation of vocabulary, as well as to identify typical means of expressive-stylistic representation concepts such as theatrical, military metaphors, metaphors of slavery, hunting, zoometaphor, phytometaphor, etc. The representation of the concept of "Muslim world" in media discourse served as material for the analysis of special techniques of manipulation of public consciousness, with the help of which ideas about Muslims are distorted, deliberately false stereotypes are formed or imposed: the technique of "hanging labels", the technique of "red rags", the use of neologisms, the technique of distortion facts, information manipulation tactics.

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